

Diagnostics of the Beal Conjecture proof in medical psychology (summary of mathematical solution)

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This is the abstract of mathematical solution of the Beal Conjecture (Generalized Fermat's Last Theorem) obtained in diagnostics of higher mental functions of man during the process of mental proving [1-5]. It is intended to give an exact and correct material for those who want to get the machine proof of the Fermat theorem.

Let us write Generalized Fermat's Last Theorem suggested by A. Beal [6] in the form:

$$z^n = x^n + y^n \quad (1)$$

with positive integers z, x, y , and $n > 2$ simultaneously having the next spectrum of independent values $n = (m, p, q) \geq 3$ for each term. The Beal Conjecture [6] states: if equality (1) is true, then z, x, y have a common factor d . In fact, it postulates scaling of equation (1) that means: if the generalized equation (1) exists as a sum of natural numbers $C = A + B$ with $C = z^n, A = x^n, B = y^n$, then A, B, C have a common denominator z^{m-1} . So natural number z can be split only into the sum of natural numbers owing to scaling of equation (1) in the paradigm of quantum mathematics [1] (if it is not so, then (1) cannot be written in natural numbers).

Let us show now that (1) has a structure of Pythagorean equation with whole numbers. For that, rewrite (1) in the next view: $(z'd)^m = (x'd)^p + (y'd)^q$, where z', x', y' coprime, and d common whole factor, and fulfill scaling down: $(z'd)^2 = (x'd)^p / (z'd)^{m-2} + (y'd)^q / (z'd)^{m-2} = (x')^p d^{p-m+2} / (z')^{m-2} + (y')^q d^{q-m+2} / (z')^{m-2} = x_o^2 + y_o^2$, where x_o^2 and y_o^2 with appropriate d are squares of some whole numbers. This is proved by the following computation.

Rewrite (1) in the next form:

$$z^m = x^p + y^q = (x^{p/m})^m + (y^{q/m})^m = z^{m-2} (x_o^2 + y_o^2) = \mathbf{x}^m + \mathbf{y}^m \quad (2)$$

Show now that \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} in (2) can be whole with appropriate d .

Take Euclid's geometrical theorem describing surface fractal (Fig.1) in the view of two chains of proportions connected with each other with equality: $z=k+l$ obtained from scaling down of (1): $z=(z'd) = (x'd)^p / (z'd)^{m-1} + (y'd)^q / (z'd)^{m-1} = (x')^p d^{p-m+1} / (z')^{m-1} + (y')^q d^{q-m+1} / (z')^{m-1} = k + l$, where k, l whole numbers when $d = (z')^{m-1}$ (d can consist of other calibration multipliers exposed in the process of infinite descent suggested by Fermat: $d = d_1 d_2 \dots$):

$$\begin{aligned} z/x_o &= x_o/k = k/k_1 = \dots = k_{m-3}/k_{m-2}, \\ z/y_o &= y_o/l = l/l_1 = \dots = l_{m-3}/l_{m-2}, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

z, x_o, y_o – integers from (2), m – natural index at least 3, $z = k + l$, k и l – whole numbers obtained from scaling:

$$z = (z'd) = (x')^p d^{p-m+1} / (z')^{m-1} + (y')^q d^{q-m+1} / (z')^{m-1} = k + l$$

If exponents p and q more or equal m , then k and l are whole with d tuple $(z')^{m-1}$. If p and q less m , then z cannot be whole.

One can get the next formulae from proportions (3):

$$\begin{aligned} x_o^2 = kz &= (k_1 z / x_o) z, \quad x_o^3 = k_1 z^2 = (k_2 z / x_o) z^2, \quad \dots, \quad x_o^m = k_{m-2} z^{m-1}, \\ y_o^2 = lz &= (l_1 z / y_o) z, \quad y_o^3 = l_1 z^2 = (l_2 z / y_o) z^2, \quad \dots, \quad y_o^m = l_{m-2} z^{m-1}, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

After scaling up we get in (4): $k z^{m-1} = k z z^{m-2} = x_o^2 z^{m-2}$, $l z^{m-1} = l z z^{m-2} = y_o^2 z^{m-2}$, and $z^m = x^p + y^q = (x^{p/m})^m + (y^{q/m})^m = (k + l) z^{m-1} = z^{m-2} (x_o^2 + y_o^2) = \mathbf{x}^m + \mathbf{y}^m$, where \mathbf{x}^m and \mathbf{y}^m are whole as squares of mean proportionals between k and z^{m-1} , l and z^{m-1} . From this it follows that x_o^2 and y_o^2 are squares of whole numbers. After scaling down (1) we have two equations with d tuple $(z')^{m-1}$ and d^2 tuple $(z')^{m-2}$:

$$z = (z'd) = (x')^p d^{p-m+1} / (z')^{m-1} + (y')^q d^{q-m+1} / (z')^{m-1}, \quad (5)$$

$$z^2 = (z'd)^2 = (x')^p d^{p-m+2} / (z')^{m-2} + (y')^q d^{q-m+2} / (z')^{m-2} \quad (6)$$

With p and q equal m , we get primitive Pythagorean triple $(z')^{m/2}, (x')^{m/2}, (y')^{m/2}$ for equation $(z')^m = (x')^m + (y')^m$ which corresponds to (5) and (6) with calibration factor $d = (z')^{m-2}$. It means that (5) and (6) are the same equation having structure of partition of whole number into sum of other whole numbers and simultaneously structure of Pythagorean equation with whole numbers. Thus $x_o^2 = (x')^p d^{p-m+2} / (z')^{m-2}$ and $y_o^2 = (y')^q d^{q-m+2} / (z')^{m-2}$ are squares of whole numbers defined by whole \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} in (2) with calibration $d^2 = (d_1 d_2 \dots)^2$. In other words, geometrical structure of equation (1) predetermines Pythagorean triples for that equation if (1) and its analogues exist.

Thus generalized equation (1) comes to the hypothetical equation with the same exponents m when $p, q \geq m$ (when p, q less m , number z from (1) cannot split into sum of natural numbers and equation (1) with whole z, x, y cannot exist):

$z^m = x^m + y^m$, $m \geq 3$, from (2) with whole $x = x'd$, $y = y'd$, $z = z'd$, and whole factor d which can be represented as composition of prime factors.

One can get now solution of the Beal Conjecture in full volume. Let us write the Fermat theorem in its usual form of hypothetical equality:

$$z^n = x^n + y^n, n > 2, x, y, z, n \text{ natural numbers} \tag{7}$$

Suppose that solution (7) exists. Let us try to construct this solution and convince in its impossibility. Apply Euclid's geometrical theorem in the view of two chains of proportions connected with each other with equality $z=k+l$. Repeat calculation (3) – (4) changing index m for n :

$$\begin{aligned} z/x_0 &= x_0/k = k/k_1 = \dots = k_{n-3}/k_{n-2} \\ z/y_0 &= y_0/l = l/l_1 = \dots = l_{n-3}/l_{n-2} \\ kz &= x_0^2, k_1z = x_0k, k_2z = x_0k_1, \dots, k_{n-2}z = x_0k_{n-3} \\ lz &= y_0^2, l_1z = y_0l, l_2z = y_0l_1, \dots, l_{n-2}z = y_0l_{n-3} \\ x_0^2 &= kz = (k_1z/x_0)z, x_0^3 = k_1z^2 = (k_2z/x_0)z^2, \dots, x_0^n = k_{n-2}z^{n-1} \\ y_0^2 &= lz = (l_1z/y_0)z, y_0^3 = l_1z^2 = (l_2z/y_0)z^2, \dots, y_0^n = l_{n-2}z^{n-1} \end{aligned}$$

Further, one can get one partition of z^n into three summands for the given whole

$$x_0, y_0, n > 2 : z^n = x_0^n + y_0^n + \lambda_n, \tag{8}$$

where $\lambda_n = z^{n-1} [(k - k_{n-2}) + (l - l_{n-2})]$ is residue after subtracting x_0^n и y_0^n from z^n , such that $\lambda_n > 0$, $n > 2$ and $x_0 y_0 \neq 0$, $\lambda_n = 0$, $n = 2$ and $x_0 y_0 \neq 0$, $x_0, y_0 \in [0, z]$, $z \in (0, \infty)$. Equality (8) represents by itself partition of z^n equal to partition (7) with the same x_0, y_0 . So (7) and (8) are equal similar partitions written in the form:

$$z^n = x_0^n + y_0^n + \lambda_n = z^{n-2} (x_0^2 + y_0^2) = x^n + y^n \tag{9}$$

Considering (9) one can note that $x_0^n \neq z^{n-2} \cdot y_0^2 = y^n$, $y_0^n \neq z^{n-2} \cdot x_0^2 = x^n$, $x_0^n \neq z^{n-2} \cdot x_0^2$, $y_0^n \neq z^{n-2} \cdot y_0^2$. Hence:

$$x_0^n + y_0^n = (x^n \text{ or } y^n) \text{ and consequently } \lambda_n = (y^n \text{ or } x^n) \tag{10}$$

Return now to the presupposition at the beginning of the proof that whole solution (7) exists. This presupposition is grounded if only concrete solution (10) in whole numbers exists. To check the truth of (10), it is necessary to construct it with help of the same reasoning as before as (7) and (10) identical by its properties. This procedure can be done till infinity in the direction of decreasing of whole numbers under condition that succession of decreasing equalities never comes to an end and numbers x_0, y_0 in (9) always be whole. However infinite succession of chained equalities (10) leads to infinite decreasing of positive whole numbers that is impossible and therefore suggestion about whole solution of (1) or (7) is not valid for any finite x, y, z, d . This is the end of the proof.

Conclusion: no one can manage to straighten curve (7) in whole numbers on line segment. The picture of surface fractal for Euclid's geometrical theorem is given on Fig.1 (coordinate axes designated as Φ^1 and Φ^2 , other symbols explained in the text).

Fig.1

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